

PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDY OF KAPIKACHHU SEED (MUCUNA PRURIENS (L.) DC.) CULTIVATED THROUGH HYDROPONICS SYSTEM - DEEP WATER CULTURE (DWC)

Dr. Kaushik Nakum^{1*}, Dr. Dharmendra P. Jani²

^{*1}Second Year P.G. Scholar, Upgraded P.G. Department of Dravyaguna, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

²Associate Professor, Upgraded P.G. Department of *Dravyaguna*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

Article Received on 02 October 2025,
Article Revised on 22 October 2025,
Article Published on 01 Nov. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17538862>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Kaushik Nakum

Second Year P.G. Scholar, Upgraded
P.G. Department of Dravyaguna,
Government Ayurved College,
Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Kaushik Nakum*,
Dr. Dharmendra P. Jani. (2025).
PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDY OF
KAPIKACHHU SEED (MUCUNA PRURIENS
(L.) DC.) CULTIVATED THROUGH
HYDROPONICS SYSTEM - DEEP WATER
CULTURE (DWC). World Journal of Pharmacy
and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(11), 702–710.
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ABSTRACT

Background - *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) is a widely recognized medicinal plant in Ayurveda, valued for its broad therapeutic applications. It is commonly employed in managing Parkinson's disease, neurological disorders, infertility, and is also revered as a powerful rejuvenating tonic. Conventionally, *Mucuna pruriens* is propagated in soil-based agricultural systems; however, the adoption of advanced soilless cultivation techniques such as hydroponics presents a sustainable alternative to mitigate constraints associated with soil-borne pathogens, yield fluctuations, and the progressive reduction of cultivable land resources. Among hydroponic methods, Deep Water Culture (DWC) is a hydroponic technique in which plant roots are continuously immersed in a nutrient-enriched aqueous solution, providing essential nutrients and oxygen directly to the roots, thereby ensuring optimal growth and enhancing phytochemical profiles.

Materials and Methods - For the present study, seed (wild

variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) has been selected as herbal drug. A thorough study has been carried out of seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC). including its

macroscopical and microscopical (pharmacognostical) studies. **Observation & Result** - In the present study Pharmacognostical Identification of Seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) was done which included macroscopical and microscopical features. The Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC) is creamish white, oval, smooth in touch and odourless. In the transverse section of the seed, several features were observed, including in TS of Testa Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchymatous cell, starch grain and in TS of cotyledon Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchymatous cell, starch grain and oil globules.

Conclusion: The structures which are observed here help in correct identification of seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) In this study, *Kapikachhu* Seed (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC) were found to be (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.). botanically compared with standard reference. No new structures were found during microscopy.

KEYWORD: Hydroponics, Deep Water Culture (DWC), *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.), Medicinal plants, Cultivation.

INTRODUCTION

The word 'Hydroponics' comes from the Greek term's 'hydro', meaning *water*, and 'ponos', meaning *labor*.^[1] Hydroponics, a soilless cultivation technique that supplies essential nutrients directly through aqueous solutions, has gained prominence as a sustainable approach to address soil-related limitations. Among the various hydroponic systems, Deep Water Culture (DWC) is particularly noted for its operational simplicity and efficiency. In this system, plant roots are continuously immersed in a nutrient enriched solution, promoting rapid growth and high yields with minimal maintenance, though it necessitates constant aeration and precise nutrient regulation. This controlled environment not only optimizes plant growth and uniformity but also enhances phytochemical accumulation while minimizing the risk of soil-borne diseases and pesticide contamination. For medicinal plants such as *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.), the adoption of hydroponic systems like DWC may help maintain or even elevate the concentration of bioactive compounds, thereby strengthen their therapeutic value in both traditional and modern medical contexts.

Kapikachhu (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.), also known as *Atmagupta*, is a revered herb in Ayurveda, traditionally celebrated for its potent aphrodisiac, strength-promoting, and rejuvenating properties. *Kapikachhu* is well-documented in various Ayurvedic texts, with

references found across multiple *Samhitas* and *Nighantus*, highlighting its aphrodisiac, rejuvenative, and neurological benefits. Rich in L-DOPA and other bioactive compounds such as tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds.^[4] *Kapikachhu* has been widely used to enhance male fertility, improve testosterone levels, and boost muscular strength and endurance. Known as the "athlete's friend," this herb supports lean muscle development, reduces fat accumulation, and enhances physical performance. Additionally, it has mood-elevating effects and has shown benefits in managing depression and increasing libido. Beyond its aphrodisiac potential, *Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) is pharmacologically significant in the management of conditions such as Parkinsonism, diabetes mellitus, rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, menstrual disorders, and tuberculosis.^[2,3] As a legume of the Fabaceae family, it contributes to soil fertility by fixing atmospheric nitrogen. *Kapikachhu* is well-documented across classical Ayurvedic texts, confirming its historical and therapeutic relevance. This review aims to comprehensively examine the Ayurvedic and modern scientific perspectives of *Kapikachhu*, highlighting its multifaceted pharmacological actions and clinical applications.

VERNACULAR NAMES^[4]

Table No. 1: Vernacular Names of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.)

No.	Region	Names
1.	Sanskrit	<i>kapikachhu</i> , <i>Atmagupta</i>
2.	English	Cowitch, Cowhage
3.	Hindi	Kaunch, Kevachh, Kevanch, Khujani
4.	Gujrati	Kancha, Kanchan, Kavatch
5.	Bengali	Akolshi
6.	Punjabi	Kawanch, Gugli
7.	Tamil	Punaippidukkan
8.	Telgu	Pilliadugu
9.	Oriya	Kaincho
10.	Marathi	Kavacha, Kuhili, Kanchkun
11.	Urdu	Kavacha

TAXONOMICAL DESCRIPTION

Table No. 2: Taxonomical classification of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.)

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Angiospermae
Class	Dicotyledoneae
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Subfamily	Faboideae
Genus	<i>Mucuna</i>

Species	Pruriens
Binomial Name	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.

AIM

To perform macroscopical and macroscopical (pharmacognostical) study of seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC) with a specially designed protocol.

OBJECTIVE

1. To study the macroscopic features of seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC).
2. To study the microscopic features of seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) were Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC) used as a drug material. A detailed macroscopic and microscopic study of seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) were carried out to establish the correct identity of the seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) by comparing with standard reference book of Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API), Part I, Vol. III 6.^[5] and Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants (Vol. 1).^[6]

The work plan was as follows

1. Plant collection and identification
2. Pharmacognosy study
 - A. Macroscopic study
 - B. Microscopic study

1. Plant Collection and Identification

Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) was Collected from the hydroponic system Deep Water Culture (DWC) established at the Medicinal Plant Cultivation and Technique Research Laboratory(MPCTRL), Government Ayurveda College, Vadodara.

Fig. 1: a and Fig. 1: c After the proper collection, The Macroscopic, Microscopic study studies were performed at Pharmacognosy laboratory of Upgraded department of *Dravyaguna Vijnana*, Government Ayurveda College, Vadodara.

2. Pharmacognosy Study

A. Macroscopic Study

The Morphological studies were carried out for shape, size, color, odour and surface of the Seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC).

OBSERVATIONS

Table No. 3: Macroscopic study of Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC).

No.	Macroscopic Characters	Observation	Figure No.	Reference
1.	Shape and structure	Oval	Fig 1.c	[i]
2.	Colour	Creamish white		[ii]
3.	Odour	Odourless		[iii]
4.	Touch	Smooth		[iiii]
5.	Taste	Sweetish-bitter		[iv]

Plate No. 1: Photos of Macroscopy of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC).

Fig 1.a Collection of *kapikachhu* seed (wild variety) from Hydroponic – DWC

Fig 1.b *Kapikachhu* fruit

Fig 1.c *Kapikachhu* seed

B1: Observations of transverse section of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.)

B. Microscopic study

The freehand transverse section of the Seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) was taken and slide was prepared separately using reagents Saffranine and Iodine. Various microscopic structures of transverse section (T.S.) of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) were evaluated.

Table No. 4: Microscopic study of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC).

No.	Types	Characteristics of Seed of <i>Kapikachhu</i> (<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.)	Figure no.
1.	TS of Testa	Epidermal cell	Fig 2.a
2.		Bearer cell	Fig 2.b
3.		Parenchymatous cell	Fig 2.c
4.		Starch grain	Fig 2.d
5.	TS of cotyledon	Epidermis	Fig 2.f
6.		Parenchyma	Fig 2.e
7.		Starch grain	Fig 2.g
8.		Oil globules	Fig 2.h

Plate No. 2: Photos of Microscopy of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC).

(A) T.S. of Testa

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Kapikachhu (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) is an important plant which is used in many diseases mentioned in Ayurvedic system of Medicine literature.

In the present study Pharmacognostical identification of Seed (wild variety) of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC) was done which included macroscopical, microscopical features of the same.

The Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC) is creamish white in colour, oval, smooth in touch and odourless. In the transverse section of the seed, several features were observed, including in TS of Testa Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchyma cell, starch grain and in TS of cotyledon Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchyma cell, starch grain and oil globules.

CONCLUSION

The Pharmacognostic characterization of the of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Deep Water Culture (DWC) sample confirms the identity of the plant as a *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.). In this study macroscopic

characters oval Shape and structure, creamish white, odourless, smooth in touch, Sweetish-bitter in taste were found and in microscopic characters including in TS of Testa Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchymatous cell, starch grain and in TS of cotyledon Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchymatous cell, starch grain and oil globules were found so, this given seed (wild variety) of *kapikachhu* correct identify of the plant as a *kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.). No new structure found rather than standard reference given for identify of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors express their sincere gratitude to the Department of AYUSH, the Principal of Government Ayurveda College, the Head of Department, all faculty members, students, and colleagues of the upgraded Department of Dravyaguna and Government Ayurveda College for their generous support and cooperation.

Institute: Government Ayurveda College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

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